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A Flexible and Robust Deep Learning-Based System for Solar Irradiance Forecasting

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ABSTRACT Most studies about the solar forecasting topic do not analyze and exploit the temporal and spatial components that are inherent to such a task. Furthermore, they mostly focus just on precision and not on other meaningful features, such as flexibility and robustness. With the current energy production trends, where many solar panels are distributed across city rooftops, there is a need to manage all this information simultaneously and to be able to add and remove sensors as needed. Likewise, robust models need to be able to cope with (inevitable) sensor failure and continue producing reliable predictions. Due to all of this, solar forecasting models need to be as decoupled as possible from the number of data sources that feed them and their geographical distribution, enabling also the reusability of the models. This article contributes with a family of Deep Learning models for solar irradiance forecasting complying with the aforementioned features, i.e. flexibility and robustness. In the first stage, several Artificial Neural Networks are trained as a basis for predicting solar irradiance on several locations at the same time. Thereupon, a family of models that work with irradiance maps thanks to Convolutional Long Short-Term Memory layers is presented, obtaining forecast skills between 7.4% and 41% (depending on the location and horizon) compared to the baseline. The latter family comes with flexibility and robustness features, which are required in large-scale Intelligent Environments, such as Smart Cities. Working with irradiance maps means that new sensors can be added (or removed) as needed, without requiring rebuilding the model. Experiments carried out show that sensor failures have a mild impact on the prediction error for several forecast horizons.

INDEX TERMS Convolutional long short-term memory (Conv-LSTM), deep learning, irradiance map, solar irradiance, time series forecasting.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

During the past decade, the field of solar forecasting has emerged due to the increasing energy demands by industry and research institutions in the context of the so-called Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Obtaining reliable, fine grain predictions is crucial for the development of many renewable energy systems. An example is the optimization of the layout and orientation of the solar panels of a Photovoltaic (PV) plant, which can have a big impact on the overall amount of energy produced during its lifetime. As the number of PV plants grows vastly and they are integrated into the electric

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grid, anticipating the amount of energy produced is needed to avoid overloads and foresee energy shortage. Furthermore, the management of batteries to accumulate the produced energy requires accurate forecasts.

Several methods are being explored in the field to this aim, which could be grouped as: Numerical Weather Prediction (NWP), image-based, statistical, and Machine Learning (ML). They could also be classified based on their characteristics, meaning if a method takes into account spatio-temporal features, if it is deterministic or probabilistic, if it considers exogenous inputs (other inputs such as physical variables) or just its data features, etc.

The task of solar forecasting inherently presents many angles of complexity. On the one hand, time granularity directly impacts on the variability of the measurements, in the

sense that, for instance, less time between recordings translate into spikes that look like noise, or the number of previous instants that are considered as the input for each inference step, i.e. the timestep, is also a relevant hyperparameter to take into account. On the other hand, forecast horizons should be established depending on the purpose of the predictions. Finally, it is also noteworthy that irradiance received at a particular location is related to irradiance recorded nearby, which can provide valuable information for predictive models.

Despite the extensive literature on the topic, there are still challenges to be tackled. The main desired features for systems that perform solar forecasting are:

- **Precision:** Most accurate possible forecast. Precision needs to be calculated using a well-accepted reference metric in order to be comparable with other works.
- **Flexibility:** Adaptability to accept a different number of inputs/outputs, e.g. add and remove new sensors as necessary. Any variation in the number or distribution of the sensors should not mean that the system needs to be redefined and trained from scratch.
- **Robustness:** Properties of a system that allow it to tolerate disruptions in the external environment without malfunctioning or changing its structure or dynamics [1], e.g. ability to recover from sensor failure and continue producing reliable predictions.

None of the published works cover all these characteristics to the best of the authors' knowledge. Firstly, precision needs to be ranked based on a common and robust metric due to the numerous dimensions of this problem. The forecast skill is widely accepted as such, and more and more works in the field are starting to use it, as pointed out by Yang [2]. However, flexibility and robustness features are usually neglected.

Deep Learning (DL) is considered as a subset of ML in which Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) are more sophisticated and approximate some complex functions better than other traditional ML algorithms. These networks are characterized by having a high number of layers, each of them representing a certain function defined by its weights and biases. The composition of all those functions results in the final function inferred by the network, which is then fitted to the available data. Therefore, these kinds of models are usually known as Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). In the last years they have gained a lot of attention due to their performance in difficult tasks, such as object classification, object segmentation, sequence prediction, or original content generation. As for solar irradiance and photovoltaic forecasting, some examples where DL has successfully been applied are [3] (using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks), [4] (employing Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) networks) and [5] (with the aid of convolutional layers for PV power forecasting).

This article aims to present a DL system to predict short-term standardized Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) or Clear-Sky Index (CSI) with no exogenous inputs, complying with the aforementioned characteristics, which will be

addressed throughout the sections. The motivation for the development of such a system is to contribute towards applications that reliably forecast short-term (up to 1-hour ahead) solar irradiance in a flexible and robust manner, in order to be deployed in PV plants or even smart cities. The proposed system can be key for critical decision making, on issues such as:

- Location of a PV plant for maximizing profitability.
- Layout of the solar panels on a PV plant.
- Optimization of energy accumulation and distribution.
- Avoiding network overloads and power cuts.
- Electricity price forecasting.
- Planning of solar panels maintenance.

As will be seen, the DL-based system presented in this work contributes along the following lines:

- Harnessing of the spatial and temporal components of the solar irradiance forecasting task. The model works with several nearby stations at once, both as input and output. Furthermore, it considers several previous and future instants by leveraging recurrent layers.
- Flexibility in the interface, while still providing competitive precision figures. The number of sensors can vary without changing the structure of the model thanks to the use of irradiance maps.
- Recovery of missing radiation figures by filling them based on nearby stations (or previous records when necessary), making it robust to sensor failure.

The structure of this article is as follows: Section I-B states the problem, and Section I-C summarizes relevant related works. Section II presents the basic definitions, the persistence model, and the skill metric that will be used later on. Section III starts by describing the data used in the experiments (Sections III-A and III-B) to later present the base networks and the family of models that were developed (Sections III-C1 and III-C2, respectively). Afterward, the precision is evaluated in Section III-D1, the correlation between location and skill is studied in Section III-D2, and Section III-D3 covers the robustness assessment that was performed to the second family of models and their intrinsic flexibility. The experimental setup is depicted in Section III-E1 and the main results are showed in Section III-E2. Finally, Section IV presents the discussion, to finish afterward with the main conclusions and future work in Section V.

B. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The problem studied in this work can be stated as a time series forecasting one: given a set of historical solar irradiance measurements from several ground sensors, predict their future values for different horizons. Some works, like the one of Wan *et al.* [6], study the topic of correlated time series prediction. Nevertheless, the correlation between nearby solar irradiance time series is stronger, since the distance between sensors play an important role. As will be explained in Section III-C2, interpolating irradiance maps and stacking them consecutively on several timesteps provides a way of

incorporating time and spatial dependencies, while adding flexibility and robustness (see Section III-D3).

C. RELATED WORK

There is a clear growing interest in the field of solar forecasting, proven by the number of works published in the topic during the last decade [2]. As mentioned in Section I-A, some apply NWP models, others make use of satellite images, and also statistical methods are widely studied. For instance, Arbizu-Barrena *et al.* [7] focus on the cloud index to forecast solar irradiance with the aid of an NWP model. Ayet and Tandeo [8] aim to forecast solar irradiance based on geostationary satellite images. A different strategy is using data produced by PV plants to build statistical models for solar forecasting. An example is a study carried out by Amaro e Silva and Brito [9], which makes use of Auto Regressive models with eXogenous inputs (ARX) to shed light on how solar data from neighboring locations can enhance predictions for a single location. They show that for short-term forecasts (up to a few minutes) neighboring information is beneficial for the prediction, but for further horizons, this effect is diminished. In Section III-C2 it is shown how to take advantage of this concept using irradiance maps, and Section III-D2 carries out a similar spatial analysis to that one of Amaro e Silva and Brito [9].

Besides those methodologies, ML approaches (and more specifically DL ones) are gaining attention in the field. As early as in the work by Hontoria *et al.* [10], the use of ANNs for solar forecasting is already present. As a more recent example, Alzahrani *et al.* [3] employ LSTM networks for high resolution forecasting (100Hz) on a single location, obtaining an Root-Mean-Squared Error (RMSE) of 0.086. The data they use comprise four days with different weather conditions (clear sky, few clouds, scattered clouds, and overcast). Qing and Niu [11] also take advantage of the temporal aspect of solar forecasting by LSTM networks, obtaining between 18.3% and 42.9% more accurate results than the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). However, the time granularity they work with is quite coarse, and the horizon is far to be applied to PV systems. Using hourly weather data (exogenous inputs) from a certain day, the model attempts to predict hourly GHI for the next day at a single location. Wang *et al.* [4] include PV data besides weather information, and feed them to a GRU network, which follows a similar logic to LSTMs. They start by analyzing the correlation between the PV power at a given instant and the n previous ones, to later use the K-means algorithm to cluster the training data into categories based on data features. Afterward, several GRU networks (as many as the number of clusters) are trained independently to forecast solar irradiance, always obtaining an RMSE of about 0.07.

When considering the time-dependent elements of solar forecasting, emphasis should be placed on the timesteps and the forecast horizons. Time resolution is also important since it introduces higher variability as its frequency increases. The main contributions of Galicia *et al.* [12] are the development

of an ensemble of different ML models and the analysis of which is the most convenient timestep for two use cases. As for the horizons, the ensemble makes predictions of the next 20 instants (sampling every 30min), although this is broken down into as many sub-problems as the number of forecast horizons. Additionally, they focus on the scalability of their system to be suitable for big data, and thus they use the MLlib library of the Apache Spark framework. Scalability is an additional desired feature that is discussed in Section V of this work.

Despite most of these works tackle the solar forecasting problem only by its temporal component, Li *et al.* [13] attempt to harness the spatial aspect of solar irradiance forecasting. In their work, they forecast 1-hour ahead solar irradiance of a single target station, depending on the historical data of its surrounding sites. With this purpose, they train 4 echo state networks (one for each season of the year), obtaining skills that go from 1.8% in summer to 18.6% in autumn. Other works that make use of spatial attributes, such as Arbizu-Barrena *et al.* [7] or Ayet and Tandeo [8], are usually based on satellite images, which are prone to errors due to soil albedo, aerosols, and dust.

The current solar energy production trends require the flexible and robust management of several PV data sources altogether, something that all these works lack, and that is addressed throughout this work. For other related tasks, experts in the field are already taking advantage of hybrids DNNs (for instance, a combination of Variational Mode Decomposition (VMD), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and GRUs for electricity price forecasting [14]). However, more novel DNNs incorporate LSTMs on convolutional layers (i.e., Convolutional LSTM), see for instance the works of Shi *et al.* [15] and Agrawal *et al.* [16] on precipitation forecasting. The current work leverages this kind of networks by translating solar forecasting from an individual time series prediction task into an image-to-image transformation problem, as will be discussed in Section III-C2. These techniques have not yet been applied in the field of solar forecasting to the authors' knowledge.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Global Horizontal Irradiance (GHI) is the total amount of shortwave radiation received by a horizontal surface. Thus, its units are W/m^2 , and it can be expressed in terms of the Diffuse Horizontal Irradiance (DHI) and the Direct Normal Irradiance (DNI) as:

$$GHI = DHI + DNI \cdot \cos(z) \quad (1)$$

where z is the zenith angle of the sun. Let $y(t)$ be the GHI at the current instant t at a certain location, the **Clear-Sky Index (CSI)** can be expressed as:

$$CSI(t) = \frac{y(t)}{I_{CS}(t)} \quad (2)$$

where I_{CS} is the GHI for a clear day at instant t at the same location. Therefore, I_{CS} can be interpreted as the theoretical

maximum GHI, and CSI removes seasonal trends from the GHI measurement caused by the position of the sun in the sky. The CSI provides a natural way to normalize solar irradiance data, obtaining values above 0 and (mostly) below 1.

The **persistence model** is the most basic forecasting approach. As such, it is used as a baseline model for solar irradiance forecasting. It is based on the assumption that the forecasted variable will remain unchanged in the future for the **forecast horizon** h . If $\hat{y}(t+h)$ denotes the forecasted value, the persistence model can be expressed as:

$$\hat{y}(t+h) = y(t) \quad (3)$$

Smart persistence refers to a persistence model on the CSI:

$$\hat{y}(t+h) = y(t) \cdot \frac{I_{cs}(t+h)}{I_{cs}(t)} = \text{CSI}(t) \cdot I_{cs}(t+h) \quad (4)$$

Similarly to the persistence model, it bases its prediction on the previous (true) value, but it also accounts for the expected variation based on the clear-sky irradiance. For the case of data that have been standardized such as in this work, formula 4 can be generalized to allow for negative values as follows:

$$\hat{y}(t+h) = y(t) + |y(t)| \cdot \left(\frac{I_{cs}(t+h)}{I_{cs}(t)} - 1 \right) \quad (5)$$

which indeed provides the same expression as 4 when $y(t)$ is assumed to be positive.

A common metric needs to be established when it comes to comparing the goodness of several models. Usual metrics, such as RMSE or Mean Absolute Error (MAE), are not enough to fully capture many intrinsic aspects of solar forecasting [2], i.e. location, timestep, and forecast horizon. The **forecast skill (S)** criterion is widely accepted as a reference metric in the field of solar irradiance forecasting. It indicates the relative improvement over a reference model:

$$S = 1 - \frac{\text{error}_{\text{proposed}}}{\text{error}_{\text{reference}}} \quad (6)$$

In this manner, models tailored for different places and time granularities can be compared against a common and simple model, which is hard to beat for small forecast horizons.

Skill can also be expressed as a percentage, and as for the error typically RMSE or MAE is used. Usually, a simple or smart persistence model is used, the latter being denoted as **smart skill**. Whereas for short forecast horizons (up to about 30 minutes, depending on other parameters) simple persistence obtains a smaller error than smart persistence, the contrary happens for further horizons. Furthermore, when working with fine time granularities (e.g. in this work all data is collected at 1Hz and grouped into 1-minute intervals) this behavior is magnified due to the measurements variability, which had already been observed in previous works [17]. An analysis was carried out to determine which of the two persistence models is harder to be beaten for the forecast horizons considered in this work (1, 11, 31, and 61 minutes). Whilst for the first two forecast horizons simple persistence generally defeats smart persistence, the opposite happens

FIGURE 1. Location of the pyranometers relative to one another.

for 31 and 61 minutes. Eventually, skill with respect to a simple persistence model is used as the reference metric to rank all models in this work, since these differences in skill are never above 4.5%.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this section, the data that were utilized are described and the steps followed to process them are shown. Afterward, the base ANNs and the developed family of models are presented, including a precision evaluation, an analysis of the impact of location on the skill, and a robustness assessment for the latter. Finally, the experiments and results are detailed.

A. DATA DESCRIPTION

Oahu's Solar Measurement Grid dataset [18] from the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) was used for the experiments. The data comprise almost 20 months of measurements from 17 LICOR LI-200 pyranometers, which collected GHI values every day between 5 am and 8 pm UTC-10 at 1Hz. The 17 sensors were laid on the island of Oahu (Hawaii) covering an area of roughly 1km² (see Fig. 1), and they were up from March 2010 to October 2011. This means that over 32 million measurements were processed for every sensor (almost 9000 hours in total, 593 days for 15 hours every day), and later grouped every minute (see Section III-B for details). This region is usually scattered with clouds and strong dominating winds come from the northeast, which translates into high solar irradiance oscillations. A detailed analysis of this topic was carried out by Hinkelman [19].

B. DATA PREPARATION

Pre-processing the data that are later used to develop predictive models is often a time consuming though important task. The first and most obvious step is to deal with the gaps (*NaNs*). Exploring the available values it was found that

for most sensors few values were missing, whereas for one of them (the one named *ap03*) over 180 days were empty. Instead of dismissing all values for this sensor and to populate all other empty values, they were filled taking the non-empty closest value in time from the 30 preceding seconds of the same sensor. If the previous condition was not met, neighboring sensors were traversed (sorted by distance) to fill the gap with a value from the same instant of a close pyranometer. Note that GHI figures were recorded every second and that all sensors are located nearby (at a median distance of 380m).

When working with ANNs, data are often standardized or scaled to operate with values near zero, where they tend to perform better. GHI values were standardized to obtain a null mean and a standard deviation of 1 as follows:

$$y' = \frac{y - \mu}{\sigma^2} \quad (7)$$

where μ is the mean and σ^2 is the standard deviation of the recorded GHI computed for each sensor (in order to account for differences in calibration).

From here, a new dataset was produced averaging the GHI by intervals of 1 minute, which is the time granularity for all the presented models. In addition, a dataset that collects the CSI instead of the GHI was built. The Haurwitz clear sky model for GHI was used to obtain the CSI (see Haurwitz [20], [21]), which is implemented in the *pvlib* [22] Python library. The CSI is of interest for some practical applications, mainly because it removes the inherent seasonality of solar irradiance (and thus it eases the prediction task). As will be seen in Section IV, the models that work with CSI obtain slightly better results than with GHI. The code to reproduce all these calculations and obtain the datasets is in the repository [23].

C. MODELING SOLAR IRRADIANCE

The foundations of the developed models are presented in the upcoming two sections.

1) MODELING FOR SEVERAL LOCATIONS

There are two key components to take into account when trying to forecast solar irradiance: time and space. Whereas most studies focus on the former, the spatial dimension can be exploited to obtain better results: irradiance nearby a location can enhance the prediction for that particular location. This is especially true when performing short-term forecasting, as discussed in Section III-D2. Section III-C2 shows how to exploit the spatial component more richly.

Several kinds of ANNs that do not consider sensor locations were trained, tested, and compared as a basis for forecasting GHI or CSI. All of them combine data from the 17 stations as the input and forecast irradiance for the 17 locations. The most basic from the ANNs is the MLP, in which every neuron is connected to all neurons from the previous layer. They do not work directly with time series, but this kind of data can be reshaped and fed as input to this kind of networks, as pointed out by Alzahrani *et al.* [3].

Instead, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) work naturally with such data: the network iterates over a time window of fixed width (referred to as timesteps) used as input for each inference step. This means that if the timestep is fixed to be n_x , then data from instants $\{i, i-1, i-2, \dots, i-n_x+1\}$ are fed as input to the network at a given instant i . The main issue with this kind of network is the vanishing gradient problem (see Bengio *et al.* [24]). This makes the predictions too dependent on the last values of the sequence, which in turn makes the network forget the first ones. LSTM networks are a type of RNNs which have proved to behave better in this sense and to capture both long and short-term relations. Bidirectional LSTMs extend the latter by performing both a forward and a backward pass on each time window.

As mentioned before, all models were developed to predict an irradiance value for each of the 17 locations (see Fig. 1) and each of the forecast horizons at once. The RMSE metric is expressed as follows:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - y_n^*)^2} \quad (8)$$

where N is the number of instants in which the error is evaluated, y_n is the true standardized GHI (or CSI when applicable) for a certain sensor at instant n and y_n^* is the predicted value for the same instant and sensor. Note that each model needs to be evaluated on 17 locations for every forecast horizons. Thus, there are $17 \times n_y$ skill figures for each model, where n_y is the number of forecast horizons.

2) MODELING IRRADIANCE MAPS

Until now, the spatial component of the forecasting problem has not been deeply exploited, though information from several locations was combined at once. Sensors that are geographically close to each other can enhance precision. Thus, one could rethink the problem of solar forecasting by interpreting the irradiance received on an area of the earth as a 3D surface whose coordinates are longitude, latitude, and GHI. Thus, this irradiance map can be inferred by feeding a network with a series (timestep) of consecutive irradiance maps, such as the one in Fig. 2, and apply the same principles from the previous Section III-C1.

When it comes to ANNs, a type of layer that has proved to be successful when dealing with images is the convolutional kind. This layer works by performing a point-wise matrix multiplication on a sliding window of the picture (a 3D array) and passing the results through an activation function like in other types of layers. They can take advantage of the correlation between nearby solar irradiance values in the same manner that CNNs exploit the information from neighboring pixels of a picture. The convolution operation can be extended to work with a time window, like in recurrent networks, bringing together both worlds with layers such as the Conv-LSTM. This kind of network uses convolutional structures both in the input and in the recurrent transitions, and it was introduced by Shi *et al.* [15] for precipitation

FIGURE 2. Interpolated irradiance map for a certain instant. Each red dot shows a (standardized) GHI measured value by a pyranometer.

nowcasting. The proposed family of models is based on these DNNs, and it is detailed in Fig. 3. The methodology of the presented framework comprises the following steps:

- 1) In the current instant, the N available sensors collect solar irradiance data, which are used to interpolate an irradiance map of shape $r \times c$.
- 2) From there, the last n_x of these irradiance maps are stacked together to conform \mathcal{X} , the input for the Conv-LSTM network. Thus, n_x is the size of the input time window, which is known as the timesteps.
- 3) Thereupon, \mathcal{X} is passed by C Conv-LSTM layers, which are like LSTM layers but with 3D inputs. Thanks to them, a 2D convolution is applied on each instant and information is passed to the next timestep by means of the cell state.
- 4) Afterwards, the resulting 4-dimensional array is flattened and D dense layers are applied.
- 5) The last step that the network performs is to reshape this vector to obtain an array of shape $r \times c \times n_y$, where n_y is the number of forecast horizons.
- 6) Eventually, the $N \times n_y$ forecasted solar irradiance values are obtained by taking the N elements of \mathcal{Y} that are the closest ones to the N sensor locations for each horizon.

In the experiments, the values used were $N = 17$, map shapes of 8×8 and 10×10 , $n_x \in \{10, 20, 60\}$, $n_y = 3$, $C \in \{1, 2\}$ and $D \in \{2, 3\}$. As explained in Section III-D3, N was also tested for values between 1 and 16.

Irradiance maps need to be obtained to train convolutional LSTM networks. New datasets that collect irradiance maps for each instant of the original dataset were built from the standardized GHI values (see the repository [23]). The irradiance maps were computed using the nearest-neighbor interpolation. This method yields maps that resemble how clouds produce steps in the irradiance recorded at nearby locations (note the steps in Fig. 2). Furthermore, its computational

simplicity is key for real-time applications, as is shown in Section III-D3. Two different map shapes were compared and explored: 8 by 8 and 10 by 10 . The shapes were chosen so that the irradiance maps are representative of real recorded values (about 26.6% and 17% respectively).

Considering this setup, the irradiance map is represented as a grid of 8×8 or 10×10 values. Thanks to this, flexibility is accomplished: including additional sensors would only enhance the predictions by filling the gaps that are interpolated on the map. The only requirement that new sensors need to meet is being geographically contained within the map region. Regarding robustness, gaps produced by malfunctioning sensors can be filled thanks to the interpolation. This will be further analyzed in Section III-D3. As for the error formulation, 8 is applied by taking the 17 nodes of the grid that are the closest ones to the 17 sensor locations. With this approach, the RMSE and skill figures are comparable to the ones obtained with the models that were described in Section III-C1.

D. EVALUATION

This section is further split into 3 parts: precision evaluation for all models introduced in Section III-C, analysis of the impact of location on the forecast skill, and robustness assessment for the family of models that work with irradiance maps.

1) PRECISION ASSESSMENT

As explained in Section III-C1, $17 \times n_y$ skill figures are derived from each model. Box plots were obtained for all models to understand how location and forecast horizon affect the skill. Fig. 4 shows two of these plots for a model from the first family (a LSTM) and another one from the second (a Conv-LSTM). It can be observed that skill figures are very stable for forecast horizons 11, 31, and 61. However, high variability is present for 1 minute. This is further analyzed in Section III-D2. Box plots for all models can be found in the repository [23].

A summary of the models from Section III-C2 alongside their scored skill can be depicted in Table 1. They target at predicting either GHI or CSI, by providing data from the 17 pyranometers and timesteps $n_x \in \{10, 20, 60\}$ minutes on each inference step, for four forecast horizons: 1, 11, 31, and 61 minutes. That is, the input has shape $n_x \times 17$ and for the output 4×17 . The RMSE was computed for each horizon independently, both for the persistence and the studied model. From there, 6 was applied to compute their skill.

The results for the networks that work with irradiance maps are presented in Table 2.¹ The same principles were followed so that they are comparable to the GHI skills from Table 1. In this case, the inputs and outputs have an additional dimension: $n_x \times r \times c$ and $4 \times r \times c$ respectively, where r and c represent the number of rows and columns of the inputs. Maps

¹ Further experiments using 2D-CNNs and 3D-CNNs were conducted, obtaining poorer results. They are not shown here for the sake of clarity (see the repository [23]).

FIGURE 3. Diagram depicting the methodology that constitutes the DL-based framework for solar irradiance forecasting.

FIGURE 4. Box plots that show how skill varies among the 17 sensors for each forecast horizon. The left figure corresponds to a LSTM that predicts CSI with timestep 60min. The right figure corresponds to a Conv-LSTM that predicts standardized GHI in a 10×10 map with timestep 20min.

of shapes 8×8 and 10×10 were employed when developing these DNNs. A schema of the inputs and outputs for these kinds of models can be observed in Fig. 5.

2) IMPACT OF LOCATION ON THE FORECAST SKILL

An analog spatial analysis was carried out to the one performed by Amaro e Silva and Brito [9], inspired by the box-plots from the previous Section III-D1 (see Fig. 4). Namely, the question at stake is: does location have an impact on the skill obtained by a certain model? It turns out that for small forecast horizons it does. Fig. 6 depicts how skill varies among sensors for the four studied horizons for a BiLSTM that predicts CSI with 60min as timesteps.

Whereas skill figures are uniform for horizons of 11, 31 and 61 minutes, the skill obtained for 1 minute draws a big variability. The area where the grid of sensors is located is characterized by predominating winds from the northeast, as explained in Section III-A. Therefore, sensors located on the

north and east sides of the considered map get poorer skills than the ones located on the west and south sides because the latter benefit from information about new clouds pushed in by the wind. Despite *ap6* and *ap7* obtain poor results for a 1-minute forecast, their measurements and location enhance their neighbors' skill. Specifically, whilst *ap6* and *ap7* achieve skills of 4.6% and 2.4% respectively, the top scorers for 1 minute are *dh09* and *dh10* (located on the west side) with skills around 32%. For the other forecast skills, this spatial correlation is not present and differences in skill are usually below 2%. Similar results are obtained for all the other models, which can be found in the repository [23].

These results are in concordance with the findings from the abovementioned article. More specifically, further forecast horizons imply less variability in skill among sensors. Furthermore, skills from further forecast horizons are less affected by neighboring sensors and western sensors score better skills.

TABLE 1. Skills scored by several ANNs with different targets, timesteps and forecast horizons.

#	Network	Target	Ts [min]	Median skill per horizon [%]				Mean skill [%]
				1min	11min	31min	61min	
1	FC	CSI	10	19.9	21.9	23.8	27.5	23.3
2	RNN			23.3	14.6	19.1	23.0	20.0
3	LSTM			26.7	21.9	23.4	27.3	24.8
4	BiLSTM			26.1	22.8	24.8	28.6	25.6
5	FC	CSI	20	14.8	22.3	24.5	28.2	22.5
6	RNN			24.4	14.4	19.6	23.6	20.5
7	LSTM			27.3	24.3	25.6	29.5	26.7
8	BiLSTM			26.2	23.9	25.8	29.9	26.5
9	FC	CSI	60	17.2	24.7	22.5	29.7	23.5
10	RNN			24.7	16.8	21.1	22.4	21.2
11	LSTM			27.4	27.7	25.4	32.0	28.1
12	BiLSTM			25.3	27.1	25.7	32.0	27.5
13	FC	GHI	10	27.3	18.7	18.9	19.5	21.1
14	RNN			35.5	17.7	15.8	14.4	20.9
15	LSTM			33.1	19.8	19.3	19.7	23.0
16	BiLSTM			33.0	20.1	19.7	20.3	23.3
17	FC	GHI	20	29.8	19.3	19.0	19.7	22.0
18	RNN			35.3	18.5	16.4	14.7	21.2
19	LSTM			31.8	20.2	19.7	20.7	23.1
20	BiLSTM			32.9	20.2	19.9	21.3	23.6
21	FC	GHI	60	22.4	19.2	19.9	22.6	21.0
22	RNN			35.3	18.4	16.8	16.3	21.7
23	LSTM			31.3	20.6	21.9	25.9	24.9
24	BiLSTM			31.6	19.8	21.2	25.4	24.5

Types of networks: FC - Fully Connected; RNN - Recurrent Neural Network; LSTM - Long Short-Term Memory; BiLSTM - Bidirectional LSTM. **Target** expresses the predicted variable (CSI or standardized GHI). **Ts** refers to the timesteps, i.e. the number of instants used for the prediction, considering that the time granularity is 1min. As an example, a timestep of 60 means that the last hour is used as input on each inference step. The **median skill per horizon** is calculated among sensors for each forecast horizon. The forecast horizons (1, 11, 31, and 61 min) reflect the number of forecasts obtained on each prediction step, and how far in time from the current instant they are. The skill is computed with respect to the persistence model. Lastly, the **mean skill** is obtained as the average of the median skill per horizon.

TABLE 2. Skills obtained for several convolutional LSTMs with different map shapes, timesteps and forecast horizons.

#	Target	Map shape	Ts [min]	Median skill per horizon [%]				Mean skill [%]
				1min	11min	31min	61min	
1	GHI	8×8	10	31.6	19.6	19.5	19.6	22.6
2			20	32.2	20.5	20.4	21.0	23.5
3			60	31.4	20.2	20.1	21.2	23.2
4	GHI	10×10	10	30.1	19.8	20.0	20.2	22.5
5			20	31.3	20.3	19.8	19.7	22.8
6			60	30.3	19.2	19.3	19.9	22.2

Types of networks: All networks in this table correspond to Conv-LSTMs. **Target** expresses the predicted variable (standardized GHI). **Map shape** refers to the dimensions of the interpolated irradiance map. **Ts** refers to the timesteps, i.e. the number of instants used for the prediction, considering that the time granularity is 1min. As an example, a timestep of 60 means that the last hour is used as input on each inference step. The **median skill per horizon** is calculated among sensors for each forecast horizon. The forecast horizons (1, 11, 31, and 61 min) reflect the number of forecasts obtained on each prediction step, and how far in time from the current instant they are. The skill is computed with respect to the persistence model. Ultimately, the **mean skill** is obtained as the average of the median skill per horizon.

3) ROBUSTNESS AND FLEXIBILITY OF THE IRRADIANCE MAPS

In a real-world environment, one would expect to have a continuous flow of measurements streamed into a central computing facility, which then performs the inference using models such as the ones presented in previous sections. It is foreseeable that at some point one or more sensors may fail, run out of battery or stop working for any other reason. Under

this situation, it is paramount to have a system that is able to recover and continue with the inference until the problem is fixed, even if the quality of the predictions deteriorates. This is what Section I-A was referring to when discussing robustness.

Considering the setup of Section III-C2, the previous situation can be simulated to then evaluate how the error of a model evolves when one or more sensors stop working for some

FIGURE 5. Schema showing the inputs and outputs of the Conv-LSTM models: t represents time, c the number of columns (8 or 10), r the number of rows (8 or 10), n_x is the number of instants taken as input (what is known as timesteps, taking values in {10, 20, 60}min, see Table 2), n_y is the number of forecast horizons (4 in the experiments), and f represents the function inferred by the network. In short, $f(\chi)$ approximates ψ , i.e. $f(\chi) \approx \psi$.

time. With this purpose, each trained model from Table 2 was evaluated when random sensors are removed from the input by computing the skill with respect to their original error. The following pseudo-code walks through this process:

```

(1)  $\max_s \leftarrow 16$ 
(2)  $\max_r \leftarrow 10$ 
(3)  $\text{skills} \leftarrow \text{table}(\max_s \times \max_r)$ 
(4)  $\text{map\_shape} \leftarrow 10 \times 10$ 
(5)  $\text{months} \leftarrow \text{get\_test\_months}()$ 
(6)  $\text{model} \leftarrow \text{load\_model}()$ 
(7) for  $n_s \in \{1, \dots, \max_s\}$  do
(8)   for  $n_r \in \{1, \dots, \max_r\}$  do
(9)      $\text{excluded} \leftarrow \text{rand\_choice}(n_s, \{1, \dots, 17\})$ 
(10)     $\text{sse} \leftarrow 0$ 
(11)     $n_b \leftarrow 0$ 
(12)    for  $\text{month} \in \text{months}$  do
(13)       $\text{batches} \leftarrow \text{load\_batches}(\text{month})$ 
(14)      for  $\text{batch} \in \text{batches}$  do
(15)         $X \leftarrow \text{filter}(\text{batch}, \text{excluded})$ 
(16)         $\text{map} \leftarrow \text{interpolate}(X, \text{map\_shape})$ 
(17)         $y^* \leftarrow \text{predict}(\text{model}, \text{map})$ 
(18)         $y \leftarrow \text{get\_ground\_truth}(\text{batch})$ 
(19)         $\text{sse} \leftarrow \text{sse} + \sum_{\text{batch}} (y - y^*)^2$ 
(20)         $n_b \leftarrow n_b + |\text{batch}|$ 
(21)      od
(22)    od
(23)     $\text{rmse} \leftarrow \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_b} \cdot \text{sse}}$ 
(24)     $\text{skills}[n_s, n_r] \leftarrow \text{compute\_skill}(\text{rmse})$ 
(25)  od
(26) od

```

Firstly, the maximum number of excluded sensors is defined in line 1. The number of times that a certain number

of sensors are randomly excluded is set in line 2. Therefore the error is evaluated $\max_s \times \max_r$ times, and so a table of the same size is instantiated in line 3. Then, the map shape is fixed, the months in which the test is performed are set and the network is loaded. For each number of sensors to be discarded and each repetition, n_s sensors are randomly picked from the 17 available ones (line 9). In line 10, the sum of squared errors is set to 0, and the number of batches as well (line 11). For each month from the test set, batches of measurements from the 17 pyranometers are loaded. Thereupon, X is obtained by filtering the excluded sensors from every batch (line 15). In line 16, the map for that batch is interpolated using X and the map shape previously defined. The model makes its prediction in line 17 using the interpolated map, and the sum of squared errors is computed and accumulated for that batch (line 19). The batch size is also saved for the current batch. Equation 8 is used in line 23 to obtain the model RMSE once errors from all batches of all testing months have been calculated. Finally, the skill is obtained in line 24 using 6 and saved in the n_s -th row and n_r -th column of the table defined in line 3. The irradiance map that is computed in line 16 is obtained using nearest-neighbor interpolation, which is lightweight and hence eases the workload of this task. Note also that the table that collects the skills has an additional dimension besides the number of removed sensors and the repetition: the forecast horizon.

With this setting, skill should be interpreted as a worsening percentage of the RMSE with respect to the error originally scored when the network was using information from the whole set of pyranometers. Once the table has been filled out, an evaluation of how sensor failure worsens the predictions can be carried out. Skills over the 10 random repetitions were averaged independently on all forecast horizons to this aim. In Fig. 7 the number of removed sensors against the average skill per horizon is shown. Specifically, it corresponds to the last entry from Table 2 (results for other networks that work with irradiance maps are similar and can be found in the repository [23]). These results are discussed in the last part of Section IV.

It should be noted that flexibility as defined in Section I-A is accomplished thanks to the use of irradiance maps. Looking at Fig. 7 from right to left: skill improves as more sensors are incorporated into the irradiance map. Information from newly installed sensors is easily incorporated into the network in the interpolation step and improves the reliability of the map (as long as the new locations are contained in the squared area covered by the irradiance map). Similarly, removing sensors can be accomplished without redesigning the model since the shape of the irradiance map is unchanged.

E. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, the experimental setup used to develop the ANNs is depicted and the main results are outlined.

1) EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The Keras library [25] with the Tensorflow backend [26] was used to train all the models presented in Section III-C.

FIGURE 6. Skill map for a BiLSTM that predicts CSI with 60min as timesteps. Skill figures are obtained from the 17 sensors by nearest-neighbor interpolation, each chart representing a different forecast horizon. Sensor names are displayed in Fig. 1.

Several Python scripts that work together were developed to test many different configurations automatically. This robust and flexible framework helped in the development and testing phases, by varying the target variable, model architecture, timestep, forecast horizons, optimizer, learning rate, loss function, batch size, number of epochs, etc. Detailed information and metadata for each model can be found in the repository [23]. In all of the experiments, test months were chosen to cover different seasons: April, July, and December. Thus, the number of days used for the training phase accounts for ~84% of the total number of days, from whose 20% of the days of each month are used for validation. The remaining ~16% of the days were used for testing. As for the hardware, all models were trained using a Ubuntu machine with 12 cores and 24 logical processors.

2) RESULTS

The proposed family of DL-based models incorporates flexibility and robustness features, without neglecting precision. Experiments show that RMSE stays within manageable limits (especially for the further horizons) when simulating the failure of several sensors. Moreover, the achieved skills with respect to the persistence model move between 7.4 and 41%, and varying the number of sensors can easily be done without redesigning the model.

FIGURE 7. Evaluation of a robustness test for a Conv-LSTM (last entry of Table 2). Number of randomly excluded sensors against the average worsening per horizon of the RMSE with respect to the original error.

Initially, several ANNs for solar irradiance forecasting were presented in Section III-C1. These base models consist of 12 ANNs that predict CSI and 12 more for standardized GHI. Section III-D1 presents Table 1, which depicts the forecast skill with respect to the persistence model for every horizon obtained by those base ANNs. Table 1 shows that the median of their achieved skills ranges between 14.4%

and 35.5%, depending on several factors, like the forecast horizon or timesteps. Section III-D2 further disaggregates this information, showing that location has a strong impact on the forecast skill for a 1-minute ahead prediction. This fact is supported by Fig. 4 (left), which shows a boxplot of the skill per horizon, and Fig. 6, which depicts the spatial distribution of the skill across sensors.

Despite that the base ANNs provide forecasts for several horizons and integrate information from the available sensors altogether both in the input and the output, they do not consider their spatial distribution. This gap is bridged with the family of models described in Section III-C2, which works with solar irradiance maps of a fixed size instead. The latter are interpolated from the same standardized GHI measurements used by the base networks. Similarly to Table 1, the skills scored by 6 Conv-LSTMs (alongside their parameters) are shown in Table 2. Even though these models work with maps, these skills are comparable to the base ones since the RMSE is calculated using 17 locations of the grid that represent the 17 sensors. The scored skills are not penalized by the use of irradiance maps, as Table 2 shows. Moreover, the same relationship between location and skill is observed in Fig. 4 (right) for short-term forecasting. On top of that, these DNNs provide flexibility in the number of sensors used as input and output, and robustness against sensor failure, as studied in Section III-D3. Simulations were carried out to show how skill behaves when one or more randomly selected sensors stop streaming data. RMSE worsens below 10% when almost 25% of them stop working, as shown in Fig. 7.

Additional models to the ones presented in this work were studied. They can be found in the repository [23] alongside their scored skill, robustness tests, and graphs.

IV. DISCUSSION

Results show that both the base ANNs and the presented Conv-LSTM family can compete in terms of precision with other solar irradiance models from the literature, with the additional contribution of integrating several locations both as input and output. Besides, the family of DNNs introduced in Section III-C2 comes with other desired features, such as flexibility and robustness, something that rival approaches cannot provide.

In terms of the quantitative improvement of the developed models with respect to the persistence model, forecast skills of up to 44.5% and 41% are obtained by specific sensors for the base networks and the Conv-LSTM, respectively. Looking at the precision of the base ANNs, experiments show that LSTMs and BiLSTMs tend to perform better than the MLP or recurrent networks for the first family of ANNs. Remarkably, for 1-minute ahead predictions of GHI, RNNs outperform the other architectures. The comparison between LSTMs and BiLSTMs is quite even, with a slight advantage for the latter. As an example, Fig. 8 presents the true and predicted standardized GHI values for a BiLSTM on the four horizons, for a specific sensor (*dh10*) on a certain date. The network corresponds to the last entry of Table 1. The selected

day showcases two very different weather situations: whereas irradiance is very stable until around 10:30, considerable variation can be appreciated afterward, probably due to scattered clouds (as mentioned in Section III-A). Results show that using CSI as the target variable can be beneficial for the skill. For the base ANNs, the same architecture obtains better skills for CSI than for GHI on the 3 further horizons (except for the RNNs, in which the contrary holds). However, the opposite situation happens for the 1-minute forecast, i.e. GHI networks outperform the CSI ones in all cases. This is likely due to the smoothing effect inherent to CSI, as explained in Section III-B.

Regarding the different timesteps, it seems like the bigger it is, the higher the obtained median skill is, i.e. more information from the past can enhance predictions for the future. This pattern is particularly true for further forecast horizons. This situation can be observed by inspecting the rows of Table 1 that correspond to a certain model architecture. For instance, this is the case for the furthest horizon (61 minutes) of the BiLSTMs, for both datasets. For the ones that work with CSI, the obtained median skill is 28.6% for 10min as timesteps, 29.9% for 20min, and 32% for a timestep of 60min. Similarly, for GHI, it is 20.3% for 10, 21.3% for 20, and 25.4% for 60min as timesteps. Furthermore, this is the case for practically all four model architectures of Table 1 both for CSI and GHI, and horizons 31 and 61. Arguably, it can be inferred that for an h -minute ahead forecast, higher skills are obtained by providing at least a timestep of size h .

Predominant winds produce high differences in the scored skill based on the location for 1-minute ahead forecasts. However, for horizons of 11, 31, and 61 minutes this effect is smoothed, as showed in Section III-D2. Therefore, the prevailing wind direction of the region should be considered when designing a network of sensors for solar irradiance nowcasting, when possible. In this manner, placing some peripheral sensors (such as *ap06* and *ap07* in Oahu) at some locations where measurements may not be needed can enhance predictions for the other (possibly more important) sensors, if chosen carefully.

Regarding the robustness assessment from Section III-D3, results show that even if several sensors fail, the system is still able to forecast irradiance within a manageable error. Fig. 7 shows that the RMSE never increases more than 15% of the original error when excluding information from up to 5 of the 17 sensors, which is 30% of them. Over that percentage (which is an unrealistic situation that never happened in the studied dataset), performance diminishes much more for the 1-minute ahead forecast than for the other horizons. Significantly, not only they tolerate sensor failure and the addition of new ones thanks to the DNNs that work with irradiance maps, but also their forecast precision worsens little for the three further horizons. Specifically, for the 11min forecast, skill stabilizes at $\sim 6\%$. Remarkably, for 31 and 61 minutes, skill worsening halts when excluding more than 11 sensors. This could be partially explained because further horizons involve higher complexity for the forecast, and therefore are

FIGURE 8. True vs predicted standardized GHI of the station *dh10* for the BiLSTM with timestep 60min. Each plot corresponds to one of the four forecast horizons: 1, 11, 31, and 61 minutes. Note that the different horizons influence on the times of the predicted GHI: for instance for 1 minute it spans from 6:00 to 18:59, whereas for 61 minutes it goes from 7:00 to 19:59.

less precise. Furthermore, a possible additional reason for this behavior is that neighboring sensors influence less in the predictions for further horizons, as shown in Section III-D2.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This work presents several Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) for solar irradiance forecasting which are not bound to the specific number of available sensors or their distribution, but rather constitute a flexible system that can recover from sensor failures. Hence, if new sensors are installed or any of the existing ones fail during some time, the system can still forecast irradiance on all locations thanks to the information from the neighboring stations, without redesigning or retraining the model. These benefits are derived from the use of solar irradiance maps and the spatial component of solar forecasting.

The presented models were shown to provide precision on the forecasted values, flexibility for incorporating or removing information from sensors and robustness in the precision against sensor failure thanks to the integration of spatio-temporal features. These features are essential for risk reduction when designing a mitigation plan on a Photovoltaic (PV) plant, since the predictions are still valid even when several sensors stop working.

Nevertheless, there is always room for improvement and some research questions related to this work are still open, namely:

1. *Is the flexibility exhibited by the developed Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) able to cope with abrupt changes in the wind direction?*

A key outcome of this work is that the developed DNNs manage to be flexible enough to handle additional sources of data and adapt to sensor failure while scoring competitive figures in the forecast skill. Precision can exceed a 40% improvement over the persistence model for the first horizon (1 minute), 25% for middle ones (11 and 31 minutes), and

30% for the furthest considered forecast horizon (61 minutes). It is also remarkable how strong the correlation between location and the achieved skill is for short-term forecasting. Abrupt changes in the wind direction could impact the skill figures negatively, especially for the sensors located on the west side of the map. It could be of interest to analyze how the Root-Mean-Squared Error (RMSE) behaves for days with predominant winds coming from the west or south sides of the map.

2. *Could the proposed approach be scalable?*

In this context, scalability can be defined as the ability to cope with the computational demands of an increase in the number of sensors. Scalability is the cornerstone in the context of smart cities, where several hundreds of thousands of nodes are interconnected to accomplish a common task. Under this premise, more resilient solutions based on High-Performance Computing (HPC) should be applied to tackle such problems. An example of this is the deployment of sensors to report the fill level of rubbish bins under the URBAN-WASTE EU project [27]. Waste collection and management can be optimized thanks to this system. The work by Grodi *et al.* [28] is another example, where several sensors distributed across parking spots work together with a central database to provide real-time information on free parking spots. Huang *et al.* [29] is yet another example, where the authors combine Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for PM_{2.5} forecasting. Thinking of a city with many solar panels located on rooftops, similar challenges such as scalability and vast amounts of data transfer are faced. The presented Deep Learning (DL) system could be integrated with those solar panels to predict solar irradiance maps from the available solar irradiance data on each moment. Therefore, the approach described in this article will be explored in future work using bigger irradiance maps. Map shapes not bigger than 10 × 10 were used in the experiments due to the number

of available sensors in the original data, but CNNs can easily work with much bigger map shapes. This is particularly true once the training phase is done and just the inference phase is considered. Hence, a set of pyranometers alongside a standard DL setup composed of a computer and a GPU could arguably forecast irradiance for an average PV plant or a small village.

3. Could the proposed approach be portable?

Portability can be defined as the feature that allows us to transfer the system into a different location with minimum effort. Consequently, an existing model could be deployed elsewhere, provided it is properly tuned. Providing the system with this characteristic (portability) should be feasible if the covered area is similar in size. This can be accomplished using a DL technique known as transfer learning. A study could be conducted to analyze if indeed a neural network could be used in a different location with some additional training. It should be noted that the experiments carried out made use of squared irradiance maps, but CNNs accept any rectangular shape as input. This is useful for locations that, unlike the studied area from Oahu, cannot be covered with a square shape, such as a PV plant or a certain set of rooftops in a city. The use of Graph Neural Networks could also be explored to make this interface even more flexible, not limiting the sensor network to square or rectangular shapes. A different approach to portability is to study if the presented family of DNNs could be applied within other fields of research, such as the examples mentioned above in the context of smart cities.

APPENDIX COMPLETE RESULTS AND DATASETS

Further information can be found in the repository [23] in order to guarantee the reproducibility of the results and to provide the full picture:

- **Datasets:** A Jupyter Notebook is provided to reproduce how the raw data were processed since the original data from the NREL [18] are subject to distribution restrictions. The datasets that can be obtained with the aforementioned notebook include the standardized GHI and CSI sampled every minute for almost 20 months where *NaNs* have been filled, as explained in Section III-B. Also, irradiance maps of shapes 8×8 and 10×10 for the same period and with the same sampling frequency.
- **Result tables:** Skill scored by each model for every horizon alongside model hyperparameters. Additional networks to the ones presented in the article are also shown. Robustness tests that were carried out as explained in Section III-D3 yield several tables too: randomly excluded sensors, RMSE, and skill for every horizon. All these figures are also included for all networks that work with irradiance maps.
- **Graphs:** All graphs from the article plus some additional ones. These include sensor distribution map (Fig. 1), boxplots of the skill per horizon, skill maps, robustness tests, sample predictions, model representation as graphs, and animated irradiance maps.

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